

The Relay Building Fire

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1. Intro

On the afternoon of Monday 7th March 2022, a fire started in a flat on the 17th floor of the Relay Building near Aldgate East Station in East London (Figure 1). The Relay is a high-rise mixed-use building, with offices and retail on the lower floors and housing on the upper floors. During the fire, two flats on the 17th and 18th floor were destroyed. The curtain wall facade was badly damaged and large glass panels and metal elements were seen falling intact to the ground. The wooden decking on the balconies was also involved in the fire.

In this report we have summarized key information found via first-hand accounts on social media (Twitter and TikTok) and online news articles. The focus of this report is on the fire damage to the facade structure and the falling elements observed during the fire event. An investigation by the London fire Brigade is ongoing regarding the cause of the fire.

Figure 1: Satellite image of the Relay building and surrounding area. Highlighted in red the flat of fire origin on the 17th floor. Adapted from Google Maps.

1.1. The Building

The Relay building is located in a busy business area close to the City, London's financial district. The building is located between Whitechapel High St, Commercial St and Tyne Street. Whitechapel High St is a large main road with high levels of traffic, including numerous bus routes. At street level the Relay building hosts one of the exits of the Aldgate East tube station (Figure 2). This is a very busy station and foot traffic from commuters and locals near the building during working hours is high.

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Construction of The Relay was completed in 2014; the building is 79 meters in height and hosts 21 floors [1]. It is a mixed-use building, with offices on the first six floors [2] and residential apartments from floors 7 to 21. The building has also commonly been known as One Commercial Street and Crawford Building. The design of the building was completed by Broadway Malyan. Information about the major companies involved in the development and construction of the building can be found at [1]. The building main structure is of reinforced concrete. The vertical elements consist of multiple concrete cores and concrete columns, visible in Figure 3A.

Figure 2: Street map of Aldgate East station in London (left) and photo of Aldgate East tube station exit at the base of the Relay building (right). The Relay building is highlighted in yellow in the street map and the view of the photo is also indicated on the map.

1.2. The Flat

The flats involved in the fire are part of the Houblon Apartments, the affordable housing element of the Relay Building. The flat where the fire originated was located on the 17th floor on South-East corner of the building, highlighted in yellow in Figure 3A. It includes a balcony overlooking Commercial St,

Figure 3: (A) Floorplan of the Relay building, the location of the flat where the fire originated is highlighted in yellow. Adapted from [2]. (B) Floorplan of the flat of fire origin on the 17th floor, wooden balcony shaded in brown. Adapted from [3].

highlighted in brown in Figure 3B. The flat was recently on offer for rent [4], photos from the listing showing the living room, the glass facade and the balcony can be found in Appendix A.

1.3. The Facade

A curtain wall facade covers the majority of the building exterior. The aluminium framing system supporting the glass was provided by Hueck [5] and the glass panels were provided by Carey Glass [6]. Panels used in the facade was double glazed units with toughened and toughened laminate glass. The opaque sections of the facade have an external toughened ceramic panel.

2. The Fire Event

2.1. Firefighting Activities

- The fire was first observed at 3.53 pm and was extinguished at 7.07pm, around three hours after it started.
- 20 fire engines and 125 firefighters attended the fire [7].
- A 64-meter ladder was used during the firefighting activities (Figure 4).
- 70 people were evacuated from the high-rise building [7].
- One female was trapped in her apartment on the 17th floor [7] by the smoke and had to be rescued by firefighters.
- Two people were taken to hospital and two were treated at the scene [8].

Figure 4: Photo of the 64-meter ladder in use by the London Fire Brigades during the Relay building fire. Adapted from London Fire Brigade [9]. Right: View from where the photo was taken.

2.2. Fire Spread

The fire started in a flat on the 17th floor of the Relay Building and spread to the flat above on the 18th floor [10][11]. The fire spread externally due to breakage of the glass panels and ignition of elements within the facade [12]. The wooden decking on the balconies also ignited [13]. In Figure 5 we can see evidence of flaming elements within the facade (shown in red rectangles), the combustible components in flame could be the polymeric interlayer used in laminated glass panels. From Figure 5 we can also see evidence of the flaming of the wood decking on the balcony (shown in red circle). In Figure 6 we can observe the wooden balconies burning after the flames have extinguished elsewhere. Residents had previously complained about the high fire risk of the wooden balconies [14] and had asked for removal of the flammable elements [15].

Figure 5: Left: Photo of Relay fire on 17th and 18th floor. In the red circle the flames from the burning wooden balcony, in the red rectangles flames coming from the glass panels. Adapted from [14]. Right: View from where the photo was taken.

Figure 6: Flames under the wood decking of the balcony on the 18th floor. The flames inside the building seem to be extinguished while sections of the balcony are still flaming. Adapted from [16].

2.2. Large Falling Objects

During the fire, large objects were observed detaching and falling from the building from the fire floors, approximately 60 meters above street level [17-21]. Glass panels were seen falling as one large piece and shatter at impact with ground sending fragments across the street (Figure 7). Metal elements, most likely a component of the facade framing system, were seen flying. Additional photos of large falling objects can be found in Appendix B.

Figure 7: Large curtain wall panel falling from the Relay building during the fire. Adapted from [18].

2.3. Fire Strategy controversies

Residents of The Relay did not hear any fire alarms sounding prior to evacuation and were instead alerted to the incident by neighbours knocking on doors and through phone communication. The fire alarm was only sounded on the ground floor [15] of the building, as the building had a stay put strategy in place for floors 12-21 at the time of the fire. However, the fire was not effectively contained in the compartment of fire origin, instead it rapidly spread to the flat above on the 18th floor. The external fire spread resulted in a breach of compartmentation.

3. Damage to property

A three-room flat on the 17th floor of the building was destroyed (complete burnout of all combustible material) and part of the three-roomed flat directly above on the 18th floor was damaged by the blaze. Half of the external balcony on the 19th floor balcony was also damaged by the fire. Figure 8 shows the building after the fire was extinguished completely.

Figure 8: The Relay building after the fire. The glass and metal sections of the curtain wall on the 17th and 18th floor are mostly destroyed. Smoke damage is visible from floor 17 to floor 19. Adapted from [22]

3.1. The Facade

Multiple glass panels on the 17th and 18th floor were destroyed by the fire, and the frame of the curtain wall is also consumed in multiple locations as visible in Figure 9. The façade aluminium frame experienced large deflections due to the heat from the fire; in Figure 10 we can observe the bowing of the aluminium transom elements (horizontal framing elements). Large deflection in the frame can lead to detachment of glass panels as the structural pressure keeping the panels in place is lost.

Figure 9: The flat on 17th and 18th floor after the fire. All glass panels have been destroyed and parts of the metal frame supporting the glass have been consumed. Adapted from [23].

Figure 10: Curtain wall after the fire with visible extensive damage to the glass panels and the aluminium frame. Bowing of the horizontal component of the aluminium frame is indicated by the red arrow. Adapted from [24].

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Appendix A - Flat of fire origin

The fire originated from a three-bed flat on the 17th floor. Photos of the flat were available online from the flat listing on Knight Frank [4]. The living room of the flat is located on the South-East corner of the building. The two external walls of the living room are clad with a glazed curtain wall facade (Figure A1, A2 and A3). The other walls of the flat are mostly of concrete with a few window openings. The flat includes a balcony with wooden decking shown in Figure A3. Concrete columns that are part of the structural system of the building are visible in Figure A1, A2 and A3.

Figure A1: Flat of fire origin. View of the living room (left) and exit to the balcony facing Commercial St. Flat layout with camera perspective adapted from [3] (right).

Figure A2: Flat of fire origin. View of the living room and internal view on the curtain wall facade overlooking Commercial Street. The window opening onto the wooden balcony is indicated with a red arrow. Two perimeter concrete columns are visible.

Figure A3: Flat of fire origin. View onto the South-East corner of the living room and the curtain wall facade.

Figure A4: View of the wooden balcony of the flat of fire origin.

Figure A4: View of the master bedroom with window onto wooden balcony. The external walls of the bedroom are solid concrete walls with one window opening.

Appendix B – Large falling objects

Figure B1: Large falling object 1. The object in figure is probably part of the metal frame of the curtain wall facade.

Figure B2: Large falling object 2. The object in figure is probably a large section of a glass panel installed in the curtain wall facade (Adapted from TikTok @99s1ime)

Figure B3: Large falling object 3. The object in figure is a large glass panel with section of the aluminium frame (Adapted from TikTok @99s1ime)

Figure B4: Photo of large falling objects. (Adapted from London Fire brigades Twitter)